

singly more irreversible with increasing concentrations of NaNO_3 , NaCl , NaClO_4 , KNO_3 , KCl , KCNS , K_2SO_4 and $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ while it tends to be less irreversible in the case of increasing concentrations of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

A perusal of Table 1 shows that there is no regularity in the variation of $k_{f,h}^0$ values with increasing concentrations of the supporting electrolytes. Meites⁶ has hinted at the limitation of $k_{f,h}^0$ in interpreting the results. However, the influence of the concentration of the supporting electrolytes on the rate of the electrode reaction of bromophenol blue can be studied^{9,11,12} in terms of the value of the potential-dependent rate constant ($k_{f,h}$) at a suitable potential which should be such as to lie between the potentials corresponding to the foot and the plateau of the polarographic wave, because⁸ at such a potential both the rate of electron transfer and diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. In the present system this potential has been taken as -0.38 V (SCE) and the values of $k_{f,h}$ at this potential have been listed in Table 1. A perusal of the values shows that $k_{f,h}$ decreases with increasing concentrations of NaNO_3 , NaCl , NaClO_4 , KNO_3 , KCl , K_2SO_4 , KCNS and $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, while reverse is the case with $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. It follows from this that whereas in the former cases the electrode reaction tends to become more irreversible, it becomes less irreversible in the latter.

The influence of the nature of the cations and anions constituting the supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of bromophenol blue has been studied by comparing the values of $k_{f,h}$ (at -0.38 V versus SCE) at a certain concentration (0.1M) of the supporting electrolytes. The order of $k_{f,h}$ values is for cations (as nitrates): $\text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+}$; for anions (as potassium salts): $\text{NO}_3^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

The role of cations and anions of the supporting electrolytes in changing the value of $k_{f,h}$ is related with their specific adsorption on the surface of the electrode.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphasomidine Complexes with La^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Y^{3+}

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THE present communication reports the potentiometric studies on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphasomidine and its complexes with some trivalent metal ions. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphasomidine was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine in alcohol-DMF mixture for ~ 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 220°.

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and A.R. grade perchloric acid. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

Other experimental details were the same as reported earlier³.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the course of titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after 2 hr. This was further confirmed by the of a sample titration mixture from time to time.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic (OH) group which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated, Y, the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves, \bar{n}_A values at various B values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve (B vs \bar{n}_A) was plotted. The pK_1^H and pK_2^H corresponding to phenolic H and imino NH were obtained by half integral method at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. These were further corroborated by plotting the graph of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B and $\log(2-\bar{n}_A/\bar{n}_A-1)$ vs B, respectively.

From the titration curves, \bar{n} and pL values for metal-ligand systems were also calculated. From the curves (\bar{n} vs pL), $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were

determined by half integral method. As the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of all the metal complexes, except the La^{3+} and Nd^{3+} complexes, was found to be less than 1.78 log unit, they were computed by least square method. The results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEP-WISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

	$t = 25^\circ$						
	$\mu = 0.1 M$						
	Cations						
	H^+	La^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Y^{3+}	Pr^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}
$\log K_1$	8.40	8.20	7.85	7.13	7.10	6.09	5.48
$\log K_2$	3.20	5.47	5.00	4.99	5.47	4.97	4.55

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Viscosity Equation of Strong Electrolyte Solutions Involving Cube Root and First Power of Concentration and "Effective Ionic Diameter"

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It has been shown in earlier publications¹⁻³ that the expression for κ (kappa) in the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes has to be modified and the modified kappa denoted by κ_m should be expressed as $(2e^3/DkTa)^{1/3}(2n)^{1/3}$ for 1:1 electrolytes, where 'a' represents the minimum distance of approach of two oppositely charged ions and has been termed as the 'effective ionic diameter', n the number of ions per cc of a particular species and the other terms have their usual significance.

Jones *et al*⁴⁻⁶ have shown that the variation of viscosity of strong electrolyte solutions upto about

0.1 N or 0.2 N can be represented accurately by the following equations:

$$\eta_r = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots (1)$$

where η_r represents the relative viscosity, C the concentration and A and B are constants.

It follows from the work of Falkenhagen *et al*⁷⁻⁸ that $A\sqrt{C}$ in equation (1) can be replaced by $(S/\beta)\beta\sqrt{C}$, where $\beta\sqrt{C}$ stands for κ (kappa) and S and β are constants which can be calculated from theory. At 25° for a 1:1 electrolyte $\beta=0.329 \times 10^8$.

In the expression $(S/\beta)\beta\sqrt{C}$ or $(S/\beta)\kappa$ deduced by Falkenhagen *et al*, κ_m may be substituted in place of κ and the expression $(S/\beta)\kappa_m$ may be used instead of $A\sqrt{C}$ in equation (1). Thus modified, equation (1) may be written as:

$$\eta_r = 1 + (S/\beta)\kappa_m + BC \quad \dots (2)$$

Putting $n = NC/1000$, substituting the numerical values of the universal constants and expressing 'a' in Angström unit in κ_m , and since $\kappa_m = (1.22/\sqrt{a})(\beta)[(C)^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}]$, equation (2) may be written as

$$\eta_r = 1 + S \left(\frac{1.22}{\sqrt{a}} \right) \left[C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3} \right] + BC \quad \dots (2a)$$

In equation (2a), $C_0^{1/3}$ is a small constant; C_0 representing that concentration of the electrolyte at which the ion-atmosphere of the central ion and interionic attraction disappear. C_0 is very small but not zero.

At 25° the values of S recorded in Harned and Owen's book⁹ are 0.006 for NaCl and 0.005 for KCl and the values of \sqrt{a} collected from the author's publications are 2.36 for NaCl and 2.34 for KCl. Therefore, for NaCl at 25°, equation (2a), after simplification and evaluation of the constants B and $(C_0)^{1/3}$ from the experimental data, may be expressed as

$$\eta_r = 1 + [0.0031(C)^{1/3} + 0.088(C) - 0.000106] \quad \dots (2b)$$

Similarly for KCl, equation (2a) in its simplified form is written as

$$\eta_r = 1 + [0.0026(C)^{1/3} - 0.0081(C) - 0.000109] \quad \dots (2c)$$

In Table 1 are recorded the values of η_r observed and calculated [denoted as $(\eta_r)_{obs.}$ and $(\eta_r)_{cal.}$] of the aforesaid electrolytes collected from the papers of Jones *et al*⁴⁻⁶. In column 1 of the table are mentioned the electrolyte and the equation used.

It will be noticed that the agreement between the observed and calculated values of η_r is satisfactory. Satisfactory results have also been obtained with KBr, KI and NH_4Cl investigated so far. It may be pointed out that equation (2a) indicates a

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF η_r OF SOLUTIONS OF NaCl AND KCl WITH C AT 25°

		C					
		0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
NaCl	$(\eta_r)_{obs.}$	1.00043	1.00081	1.00146	1.00259	1.00544	1.00995
	$(\eta_r)_{cal.}$	{ 1.00046	1.00086	1.00144	1.00250	1.00544	1.01013
KCl	$(\eta_r)_{obs.}$	{ 1.00019	1.00030	1.00040	1.00044	1.00045	1.00025
	$(\eta_r)_{cal.}$	{ 1.00020	1.00030	1.00037	1.00045	1.00044	1.00029

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